

8T – The Coupling Constants Series and Curvature Spectra's

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Abstract:

Following the previous paper regarding on the number of fields meditating an interaction of each coupling term of the primordial coupling constants series, it is possible to expend the idea by additional parametrizing. Each coupling term has "curvature spectra" a term coined in this paper, which meant to numerate the different features of the net curvature of each coupling term. The curvature spectra is analogous to the idea of fields in Quantum field theory, described by the parameter Ψ_i , instead of the original multiplier N_V .

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

Up until now, reader is probably familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. In the 8T thesis, we have seen the multiplier of each term from the second and above, is reflecting the number of so-called "fields" of each interaction. The first coupling term has eight gluon fields:

$$8 + (1)$$

The second term has three fields, the massive W and Z bosons, in accordance to the right multiplier, marked in black:

$$[(8 * \mathbf{3}) + (3)] + 3$$

Since all we have in the 8T its curvature, author would like to coin the term – "Curvature spectra", that is each interaction has Bosonic, net curvatures which differ from one another in certain orientation. It is currently unclear which kind of a physical difference it is, it could be a difference in a orientation of the curvature, or a more obvious difference related to mass or both. The features of the W and Z bosons differ from one another supporting the idea of the spectra. Therefore, it is possible to represent the right multiplier as means of a spectrum that is to parametrize it.

$$\sum_{i=1}^{i=N_V} \Psi_i = N_V \quad (1.45)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (1.42)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

Therefore, in the 8T, instead of having a certain finite number of fields, we have an infinite amount of curvature orientations, all appear on the matrix tensor and are isomorphic to prime numbers and one. The curvature spectra is parametrized and counting the number of orientations which in physical theory account the different kinds of particles associated with each coupling term. The new elevated form of the primorial is:

$$F_R \# = \left(2^{\mathcal{M}} * \prod_{i=1}^{i=N_V} \Psi_i + (\mathcal{M}) \right) + N_V \quad (2)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)